

Providing student feedback through electronic assessment for Linear Algebra at Maseno University, Kenya

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Abstract: In this paper we report on our work to set up, use, and evaluate electronic assessment for mathematics courses at Maseno University, Kenya. This was introduced as an attempt to address the problem of providing high quality student feedback in large classes with limited support resources. We report on a first year Introductory Linear Algebra course offered in the Spring of 2019 for a class of 700 students using weekly quizzes developed with STACK, a computer aided assessment system for mathematics. Results on students' use of the system and feedback from an evaluation indicate it was effective in providing better feedback to support student learning. The approach is now being adopted by other universities in Kenya and in Africa through shared content.

Keywords: Computer aided assessment; feedback; automated assessment

1 Introduction

One of the problems affecting teaching and learning of mathematics in Kenyan public universities is high student to lecturer ratios, particularly for introductory courses. In the Spring of 2019, Dr. Oyengo was assigned a Linear Algebra class of 700 first-year students without any support in the form of teaching assistants. In addition, he was teaching a fourth-year course to 500 students. This heavy workload meant preparation time and resources for teaching were limited. In addition, it is impossible to provide any form of detailed feedback to students during the semester, due the amount of marking that would be required. As a result, students do not do regular assignments from which useful feedback that enhances learning is provided.

The School of Mathematics, Statistics and Actuarial Science (SMSAS) at Maseno University piloted the use of computer aided assessment (CAA) in teaching a Linear Algebra course. The CAA system used was STACK (System for Teaching and Assessment using a Computer algebra Kernel), which is an assessment package specifically for mathematical sciences. STACK was used as an integration to the learning management system, Moodle. The reference book used for the course was the online book "An introduction to Linear Algebra" by R. Beezer (2015). Hence, all software, and resources used were open source.

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The University of Edinburgh, through Prof. Chris Sangwin, the developer of STACK, provided support through training, sample questions, and the use of their servers for the pilot program in the Autumn of 2018.

Technical support was provided by a not-for-profit organization, IDEMS International, in authoring questions, structuring quizzes and training of Maseno staff in the authoring and editing of STACK questions. Of the 20 teaching staff in the school of Mathematics at Maseno, five attended a week long workshop on online assessment held in August 2019 at Maseno and supported by IDEMS. There has been a continued technical support to Maseno staff in the use of STACK.

This paper reports on the pilot program and its effort to address the problem of providing good student feedback in an Introduction to Linear Algebra class of 700 students at Maseno University. A background to the context in Kenya and to STACK is given. Implementation details of the construction of weekly quizzes is provided. Student data on the use of the system is presented and the implications for this on teaching at Maseno, and beyond, is discussed.

2 Background

2.1 The Context

The 2003 reforms in which the Kenyan government announced free primary education caused an increase in university enrolments. University enrolment in 2013 increased to 195,528 from 100,649 in 2012 (Ministry of Devolution and Planning, 2013). While the number of public universities has increased from 7 in 2013 to 31 now, there has not been a corresponding increase in the number of teaching and support staff. Maseno University was founded in 1990 and currently has a student population of about 12,000. In 2019/2020 Maseno University admitted 4,500 first year students, of which 400 are in the SMSAS. The SMSAS was founded in 2011 and offers six undergraduate programs, four Masters' programs and three PhD programs. It has nineteen teaching staff and four non-teaching staff. The SMSAS also provides services to other schools whose students take compulsory maths courses in the first two years of their study. As a result, these classes tend to be quite large with student numbers of 300 to 1,000.

At Maseno, lecturers are required to teach at least four classes in a single semester with no support in the form of teaching assistants. As a result, students do not have an opportunity to engage meaningfully with continuous formative assessment, and do not receive timely feedback, if any, from such assessments. Indeed, for such large classes, lecturers may give one or two continuous assessment tests (CATs) per course. In many cases, students do not receive feedback on CATs before the final exam.

2.2 Overview of STACK

STACK is a CAA system for mathematics, and other STEM subjects. STACK focuses on accepting algebraic input from students, in contrast to traditional online assessment that relies on multiple choice questions, which have a number of well-known limitations (Sangwin and Jones, 2017).

STACK separates the input validation and the assessment algorithms. Multipart questions can be written with many input boxes, and algorithms that mark various combinations of these inputs. Follow-through marking can readily be implemented as needed (Sangwin, 2015).

STACK has several important features for mathematics. STACK has very flexible input mechanisms based around algebraic input. This means students can freely enter an equation or a polynomial, and STACK can then assess the properties of this expression. This enables "Find examples of style questions, where there are many correct answers, described as a higher-order skill by (Kinnear, 2019). STACK also supports "reasoning by equivalence", where students present an argument line-by-line.

STACK can generate questions with random variables, ensuring different students see different variants of a question. This supports practice, and has been found to help reduce copying of answers.

STACK uses computer algebra to assess answers, and teachers can give partial marks and tailored feedback depending on the different mathematical properties of the students' answers. STACK has unique, specialist packages, e.g. questions involving numerical accuracy and significant figures.

STACK has been continuously developed since 2004 and is in widespread use in higher education. STACK is the most advanced open source assessment system for mathematics. Open source projects make it relatively easy to collaborate with other teams, including international collaboration in multiple languages. Indeed, developing an entire learning system from scratch would be too large a project and commercial learning systems are both expensive and usually impossible to modify.

3 Methods

3.1 Implementation of STACK at Maseno

Dr. Oyengo was introduced to Prof. Chris Sangwin by Dr. Stern of IDEMS International. Prof. Sangwin then met Dr Michael at the University of Edinburgh in November 2018 where Dr. Oyengo was introduced to STACK through a short two day training. The training focused on authoring questions and writing a good feedback, that is, showing exemplar

tasks and ways of solving standard questions. For ease of use, the University of Edinburgh offered to host the course on their servers for the pilot.

To develop new questions for the course Dr. Oyengo would propose questions for a given week and discuss with Mr. Parsons of IDEMS International who provided technical support and would author those questions in STACK. In some cases, Mr Parsons would modify the questions to introduce good pedagogical practices and take advantage of the features of STACK to make the questions more intuitive. See figure 1 below on an example question testing on the concept of a basis for a vector space. In this question, a student will first have

For what value of the number k do the following vectors NOT form a basis of \mathbb{R}^3 ?

$$\begin{bmatrix} -2 \\ 1 \\ -1 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 16 \\ -14 \\ k \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} -3 \\ 3 \\ -2 \end{bmatrix}.$$

$k =$

Fig. 1: STACK question on a basis for a vector space.

to be familiar with what a basis is, and when a given set makes a basis. There are infinitely many values of k that will result in a correct response. One of the features of STACK is to check that the set (with the students value for k) is linearly independent, and thus makes a basis. This question was an improvement on a question that just wanted students to check whether a given set was independent. With the randomization (a feature of STACK), each student would get completely different sets.

Once questions were authored, Dr. Oyengo would then proof-read and edit (whenever necessary) before publishing for students in the quizzes. Due to time constraints and Dr. Oyengo being assigned the course at short notice, questions were being developed week by week during the semester. Covering the course content was prioritized over detailed work on individual questions.

3.2 Mastery and Test quizzes

Each week, students had two quizzes to attempt; a mastery quiz and a test quiz, with 5 ~ 8 questions on each quiz. The 20 quizzes over ten weeks contributed equally to the final CAT mark which was 30% of the final grade. The main exam was 70% of the final grade and did not use CAA. Mastery quizzes were designed to help students master content taught in the respective week. They were opened at the beginning of each week and remained open until the end of the semester. Unlimited attempts were allowed, with the highest score being recorded for final assessment. Most questions had randomization, which enabled students to see a different variant of the questions with each attempt. This design was to encourage students to make multiple attempts to master the content.

Test quizzes were designed to test students understanding of the content taught in the respective week. Test quizzes would open at the beginning of each week and close at the end of the week. To ensure students had sufficiently understood the content, students had to get at least 70% on the mastery quiz to access the test quiz. Only one attempt was allowed on this quiz. The test quizzes contained similar questions, or different randomized versions of some questions from that week's mastery quiz.

4 Results

Figure 2, showing number of mastery quiz attempts, shows there was continued engagement with these quizzes. Sharp spikes occurred just before the deadline of the test quizzes, shown with vertical lines. There were also consistent attempts at the mastery quizzes after the due date of the test quizzes, shown in black in figure 2. This indicates that the mastery quizzes were used by students to genuinely master the content not just to access the test quiz, as well as prepare for the final exam, as shown by the attempts made after the final test quiz and before the final exam.

Fig. 2: Number of attempts and completion times on the ten mastery quizzes.

Figure 3 shows an analysis of the final results with the quiz results. From the graph it is evident that most students who scored more than 40% on the CATs, performed well on the final exam and passed the course. Conversely, most who performed poorly on the CATs (this was a very small percentage), did not do well on the final exam and failed the course. As would be expected, a few anomalies can be observed from the performance of a few students. In general, this analysis supports the hypothesis that the quizzes helped students in preparing for, and doing well in their final exam. As can be seen in the student feedback responses, getting immediate feedback on the quizzes was extremely useful, especially during revision.

An evaluation survey was given to students after the course through a Google Form. Many students commented on the effect of the quizzes on their understanding of the course. Here are some selected comments: “*STACK really helped me much more in understanding the course*”, “*I am very grateful for this online course because I have learnt a lot concerning linear algebra, and particularly from the mastery quizzes*”, “*Masteries helped me in improving through the course*”, “*Am strongly supporting this mode of learning because it*

Fig. 3: Student performance in the CATs as compared to the final exam.

motivates one to learn so that the content to stick in mind. This helps one to have easy time in doing the quizzes and understanding the content. All the time you have an idea of all the content in each topic of the unit. Also the review of the quizzes is very beneficial. This is because it is directing one to the right way of solving a certain problem. This helps one to identify errors and correct. According to my opinion, I would like other units related with maths to emulate this mold of learning. It is very beneficial to us students. Thank you ."

A few students thought it was too much work on their part and preferred the previous approach: *"Two sitting CATS are better than the STACK quizzes"*

When asked to rank seven aspects of the course from most to least beneficial, "Getting feedback on my answers to quizzes" and "Being able to make multiple attempts to mastery quizzes" were ranked first and second respectively.

5 Conclusion

Electronic assessment enabled students to continuously interact with problems which helped improve the mastery of content. STACK features made it possible to provide detailed feedback to quiz questions from which students could identify their mistakes and reattempt the quizzes.

Even though most of the students do not have laptop computers, they were able to access the quizzes through their smart phones. This was one of the strengths of implementing online assessment at Maseno. At the time of authorship, Maseno University has made a big stride in improving wireless internet access at its campuses. This was one of the aspects students requested to be improved upon in the survey, and it will further improve access to online educational content by students at Maseno.

At the time of authorship, four further courses at Maseno have been developed and taught with the aid of STACK quizzes. There are plans to develop more online courses with the integration of STACK quizzes, and to improve on already developed courses. There has been interest in the use of STACK beyond Maseno. Three other universities are already using the developed quizzes from this course to teach Linear Algebra.

With the support provided by IDEMS and the University of Edinburgh, implementing this project was achievable for the lecturer. With gradual development of online assessments and improvement of existing ones at Maseno, high quality teaching and learning is achievable, especially with restrictions to traditional teaching and learning caused by the COVID pandemic. In the Kenyan situation where there is a huge students to lecturer ratio, STACK could play a big role in providing feedback to individual students, where as before, this was an impossible task. This is particularly significant in the African context where support for teaching and learning is insufficient.

References

- [1] Kinnear, G. (2019). Delivering an online course using STACK. In Contributions to the 1st international STACK conference 2018 in Fürth, Germany. Fürth, Germany: Zenodo. doi:10.5281/zenodo.2565969
- [2] Ministry of Devolution and Planning. (2013). Transforming Kenya: Pathway to devolution, socio-economic development, equity and national unity. Nairobi: Ministry of Devolution and Planning.
- [3] Sangwin C. (2015) Computer Aided Assessment of Mathematics Using STACK. In: Cho S. (eds) Selected Regular Lectures from the 12th International Congress on Mathematical Education. Springer, Cham.
- [4] Sangwin, C. J., and Jones, I. (2017). Asymmetry in student achievement on multiple choice and constructed response items in reversible mathematics processes. *Educational Studies in Mathematics*, 94, 205-222. doi: 10.1007/s10649-016-9725-4
- [5] Beezer A. R., (2015). A first course in Linear Algebra. Congruent Press, Gig Harbor, Washington, USA. <http://linear.pugetsound.edu>.